

RR Lyrae Stars in Ultra-faint and Ultra-diffuse Dwarf Milky Way Companions

Clara Martínez-Vázquez, Kathy Vivas, and Alistair Walker

Searching for RR Lyrae stars (RRLs) in ultra-faint dwarf (UFD) and ultra-diffuse dwarf (UDD) Milky Way companions is important for obtaining accurate distances to these systems, which then allows determination of their physical properties (e.g., size and luminosity) and computation of their orbits. Furthermore, given that they may be among the most ancient and primitive galaxies formed (Bose et al. 2018; Simon 2019), the pulsation properties of the RRLs can provide important clues about the contribution of these systems to the formation of the halo of the Milky Way, helping us to better understand the hierarchical formation and evolution of our Galaxy.

Over the past two decades, we have witnessed the discovery of more than 50 new UFDs and the first two UDDs (Crater II and Antlia II; Torrealba et al. 2016, 2018). These have been detected thanks to large-area, deep, multi-color imaging sky surveys; those carried out with the Dark Energy Camera (DECam) on NOIRLab's Victor M. Blanco 4m Telescope at Cerro Tololo Inter-American Observatory (e.g., DES, SMASH, MagLiteS, DELVE) have so far contributed to the discovery of more than 20 UFDs. *Gaia* proper motions, spectroscopy for radial velocities and abundances, and time-series photometry are essential ingredients to allow full interpretation.

Our team has concentrated on increasing the census of RRLs in UFDs. The low mass, the scarcity of stars, and the large contamination by field stars make the determination

of morphological parameters and distances for these galaxies a challenging task. An attractive method to improve the distance determination to these ultra-faint systems—and thus to clarify their nature—is to find RRL members. As pulsating variable stars with periods ranging from 0.2 to 1.2 days, RRLs are readily identifiable with suitable time-series photometry. Since RRLs obey well-calibrated period-luminosity relations, they are an excellent distance indicator, and are observable throughout the Local Group. Moreover, since RRLs are older than 10 Gyr, they can also provide insight on the properties of the old stellar population in any systems in which they are found.

In Martínez-Vázquez et al. (2019), we have searched for RRLs in some of the DES UFD systems using *gri* time-series observations with the Goodman High Throughput Spectrograph at SOAR. We also took additional data with DECam, collecting a total of around 40 epochs per filter per galaxy. As an example of the results we have detected two RRLs in the field of Grus I (Figure 1), one in Phoenix II, and four RRLs near Grus II; however, it is clear that one of these RRLs is a Galactic halo member and two of these are more distant than the galaxy itself, and are likely associated with the Chenab/Orphan Stream. The new distances measured with the newly detected RRLs in these systems allowed us to set their location farther than previously thought, thus implying larger physical sizes for these systems.

In Vivas et al. (2020a) we extended the search to 27

Figure 1: CMD of Grus I from our Goodman/SOAR photometry. Two RRLs were detected in this galaxy at the same distance modulus of 20.51 mag. The red line shows the best isochrone shifted to the distance obtained from the RRLs. (Figure modified from Martínez-Vázquez et al. 2019).

UFDs within 100 kpc using the *Gaia* DR2 RRL catalog (Clementini et al. 2019). From proper motions, magnitudes and location on the sky, we associate 47 *Gaia* RRLs to 14 different satellites. We have identified RRLs for the first time in Tucana II; found additional members in Ursa Major II, Coma Berenices, Hydrus I, Boötes I and Boötes III; and distinguished candidate extra-tidal RRLs in Boötes I, Boötes III, Sagittarius II, Tucana III, Eridanus III, and Reticulum III. Finding extra-tidal RRLs suggests that an undergoing tidal disruption in these galaxies may have happened; however, radial velocities are needed to confirm these extra-tidal RRLs as members. We have also measured the distances to those galaxies. Figure 2 shows a comprehensive and updated analysis of the number of RRLs in dwarf galaxies. In particular, it allows us to predict that the method of finding new UFDs by using two or more clumped RRLs will work only for systems brighter than $M_V \sim -5$ mag.

In parallel, our team has also been involved in the search for RRLs in the UDD Galactic companion Crater II. The results of this project have been presented in a pair of papers (Walker et al. 2019; Vivas et al. 2020b). Crater II is impressively large—comparable to classical dwarfs like Sculptor or Fornax. It has a population of ~ 100 RRLs (Joo et al. 2018). From the spatial distribution of the RRLs in the

Figure 2: Left: Literature number of RRLs versus M_V for all the dwarf satellites in the Milky Way, Andromeda Galaxy, isolated dwarf galaxies, and two Sculptor group dwarfs. Filled symbols represent those dwarf galaxies for which the RRL search was carried out farther than two half-light radii and for which we expect approximately 100% completeness in the number of RRLs. The red line shows their linear fit. (Figure from Martínez-Vázquez et al. 2019). Right: Updated number of RRLs versus M_V for the UFDs. Red curve corresponds to the same fit as in the left panel. Note that the axes are not semi-logarithmic in this plot. (Figure modified from Vivas et al. 2020a).

sky, we have found that Crater II has an elongated shape. Using our high-quality light curves, we have obtained accurate pulsation parameters for the RRLs, which we have used to measure a new distance for Crater II of 117 ± 4 kpc. Also, when simply dividing the RRLs into two groups on the basis of whether they are brighter or fainter than the fitted fiducial in the *i*-band period-luminosity diagram, we find that the two groups have significantly different spatial distributions, with the brighter group being more centrally concentrated. The mean difference in brightness, when interpreted as a metallicity difference, is consistent with the metallicity dispersion of 0.2 dex found for the RGB members stars by spectroscopy (Caldwell et al. 2017; Fu et al. 2019) and is consistent with the relatively narrow RGB.

By stacking the best images from the same data set, we have produced a deep CMD that reaches well below the Crater II main sequence turn-off and shows that Crater II is an old system with no intermediate age or young stars (Figure 3). The subgiant branch (SGB) clearly splits in two, showing two burst events of star formation in its very early epochs. The isochrones indicate a mean age of 12.5 Gyr for the main event and a mean age of 10.5 Gyr for the brighter SGB. With such multiple star formation events, Crater II shows similarity to more massive dwarfs that have intermediate age populations. However, for Crater II, there was early quenching of the star formation, and no intermediate age or younger stars are present.

We are continuing our observations on these interesting and important systems and anticipate a harvest of new galaxies to study following the commencement of the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) on the Simonyi Survey Telescope of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory.

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Figure 3. CMD for the central field ($r < 0.78$ deg) of Crater II obtained with DECam. Orange and light blue lines represent the best set of alpha-enhanced isochrones from the BaSTI library. Pink line shows the zero-age horizontal branch (ZAHB). Isochrones and ZAHB were shifted using a distance modulus for Crater II of 20.33 mag (Vivas et al. 2020b). RRLs are displayed with purple circles. (Figure modified from Walker et al. 2019).